

Quantitative Analysis of Viscosity Deviations in Hydrogen-Bonded Binary Systems Involving 2-Propenol

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ABSTRACT

The thermo physical behaviour of binary liquid mixtures of 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol and 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol was investigated through systematic measurements of density (ρ) and viscosity (η) at three temperatures (298.15, 308.15, and 318.15 K) across the entire mole fraction range. The results reveal that both density and viscosity decrease monotonically with increasing 2-propenol concentration, consistent with its lower molecular weight and weaker hydrogen-bonding ability compared to the co-solvents. Temperature elevation further reduces viscosity, attributed to enhanced molecular mobility, expansion of free volume, and weakening of associative interactions. Experimental viscosity data were evaluated against three widely used mixing rules—Tamura–Kurata (TK), Dey–Biswas (DB), and Hind models using absolute percentage deviations. For the 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol system, the Hind equation consistently provided the best correlation, with deviations ranging from 1.00–1.88%, while the TK relation also performed satisfactorily (1.24–4.17%). Conversely, the DB model showed significant deviations, especially at elevated temperatures, reaching 21.88%. In the case of the 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol system, predictive accuracy was strongly composition- and temperature-dependent: the Hind equation performed best at 308.15 K, whereas the TK model showed superior accuracy at 298.15 K and 318.15 K. Further analysis using the Jouyban–Acree (J–A) model demonstrated excellent agreement, with standard deviations ≤ 0.071 . The signs and magnitudes of the J–A coefficients suggest that hydrogen bonding dominates in 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol, while a combination of π – π stacking and hydrogen-bond interactions governs 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol. Furthermore Hind and Tamura–Kurata models as reliable predictive tools for associating alcohol mixtures, while the Jouyban–Acree equation provides robust correlation across all conditions. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of non-ideal mixing effects and molecular interactions in binary liquid mixtures.

Keywords: Tamura–Kurata, Dey–Biswas, Hind, non-ideal mixing, viscosity, Jouyban–Acree.

INTRODUCTION

The study of physicochemical properties of liquid mixtures is a central theme in solution chemistry, as it provides valuable insights into the strength and nature of molecular interactions governing real fluid behavior. Among these properties, density (ρ) and viscosity (η) are particularly important, as they are highly sensitive to changes in composition, temperature, and intermolecular forces (Ali & Nain, 2001). Deviations from ideality in these parameters often serve as indicators of specific interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, dipole–dipole forces, and π – π stacking, which play a crucial role in determining the structure and dynamics of liquid mixtures (Redlich & Kister, 1948; Fort & Moore, 1966). The selected

components for this study **2-propenol (allyl alcohol), benzyl alcohol, and 2-phenyl ethanol** are of significant industrial relevance. 2-Propenol is widely employed as an intermediate in pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, and polymer industries due to its high reactivity and solubility (Budavari, 1996). Benzyl alcohol, a common solvent, preservative, and fragrance ingredient, is extensively used in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and coatings (O'Neil, 2013). Similarly, 2-phenyl ethanol is a naturally occurring aromatic alcohol with applications as a fragrance in perfumery and as a flavoring agent in food and beverages, as well as a solvent in drug formulations (Mishra et al., 2017). Their wide industrial use underscores the necessity of understanding their physicochemical and transport properties, particularly

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when mixed with other solvents in formulation and processing. From a molecular perspective, these systems are characterized by **associative interactions**. Benzyl alcohol exhibits strong self-association through hydrogen bonding of its hydroxyl group, whereas 2-phenyl ethanol introduces both hydrogen bonding and π - π **interactions** due to its aromatic ring. In contrast, 2-propenol, with a relatively smaller structure and weaker hydrogen-bonding ability, tends to disrupt these associations, leading to non-ideal mixing behavior. Understanding such interactions is essential for developing predictive models for viscosity, which are indispensable in chemical engineering, separation processes, and industrial formulations (Riddick et al., 1986; Marcus, 2012). Several empirical and semi-empirical viscosity models, such as those proposed by **Tamura–Kurata (1952)**, **Dey–Biswas (1973)**, and **Hind et al. (1960)**, have been used to describe viscosity behavior of binary mixtures. While these relations offer varying levels of predictive accuracy depending on the system studied, more generalized correlation approaches such as the **Jouyban–Acree model** (Jouyban & Acree, 1998) have been shown to be effective for associating and non-associating mixtures. In the continuation of previously published work **the present work aims to investigate** the effect of composition and temperature on viscosity and excess viscosity of binary mixtures of 2-propenol with benzyl alcohol and 2-phenyl ethanol at 298.15, 308.15, and 318.15 K. To assess the predictive capabilities of the Tamura–Kurata, Dey–Biswas, and Hind models through comparison with experimental data and to correlate experimental data of viscosity using the Jouyban–Acree model and evaluate its applicability for the studied systems. This work mainly focus on molecular-level interpretation of the observed deviations in terms of hydrogen bonding, dipole–dipole interactions, and π - π stacking. This integrated experimental and theoretical approach not only enhances understanding of **non-ideal mixing phenomena** but also contributes reliable data for practical applications in chemical engineering, industrial formulations, and solvent design.

Theoretical modeling

Tamura–Kurata relation: Tamura–Kurata (TK) model is an empirical approach to estimate the

viscosity of binary liquid mixtures by considering both mole fractions and volume fractions of the components along with a binary interaction parameter;

$$\eta_{TK} = x_1\phi_1\eta_1 + x_2\phi_2\eta_2 + 2(x_1x_2\phi_1\phi_2)^{1/2}T_{12} \quad (1)$$

Dey–Biswas relation: Dey–Biswas (DB) correlation represents the natural logarithm of the mixture viscosity as a composition-weighted sum of the pure-component log-viscosities plus a binary interaction contribution:

$$\ln \eta_{DB} = \phi_1^2 \ln \eta_1 + \phi_2^2 \ln \eta_2 + 2\phi_1\phi_2 \ln \eta_{12} \quad (2)$$

Where η_{DB} is the DB-predicted viscosity of the mixture, η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of pure components at the measurement temperature, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the component volume fractions, and η_{12} is an empirical binary-interaction viscosity parameter that embodies specific intermolecular effects (association, hydrogen bonding, and structure making/breaking) that can be computed by the following rearrangement;

$$\ln \eta_{12} = \frac{\ln \eta_{Exp} - \phi_1^2 \ln \eta_1 - \phi_2^2 \ln \eta_2}{2\phi_1\phi_2} \quad (3)$$

The squared weighting on the pure-component terms emphasizes self-contributions, while the $\phi_1\phi_2$ factor scales the interaction contribution with mixture heterogeneity.

Hind–Ubbelohde model: The **Hind–Ubbelohde (HU) model** expresses the viscosity of a binary mixture as a mole-fraction weighted sum of the pure-component viscosities with an additional term accounting for binary interactions:

$$\eta_{HU} = x_1^2\eta_1 + x_2^2\eta_2 + 2x_1x_2\eta_{12} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_{12} = 2 \left(\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \right)$$

The first two terms, $x_1^2\eta_1 + x_2^2\eta_2$, represent the ideal contribution of each component, emphasizing their self-effects, while the third term, $2x_1x_2\eta_{12}$, accounts for deviations from ideality caused by specific intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen

bonding, dipole–dipole attractions, or structural modifications in the mixture.

Results and Discussion

The experimental density (ρ) and viscosity (η_{exp}) values of the binary mixtures of 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol at temperatures 298.15 K, 308.15 K, and 318.15 K are reported in Table 1. The density decreases almost linearly with increasing mole fraction of 2-propenol (X_1), reflecting the lower molecular mass and density of 2-propenol compared to benzyl alcohol. The viscosity of the mixtures also decreases with increasing 2-propenol concentration, owing to weaker intermolecular hydrogen bonding in 2-propenol compared to the strongly self-associated benzyl alcohol. For instance, at 298.15 K, viscosity decreases from 5.30 m Pa·s ($X_1=0.05$) to 2.15 m Pa·s ($X_1=0.95$). As temperature increases, a systematic reduction in viscosity is observed across all compositions, consistent with enhanced thermal agitation, disruption of hydrogen-bond networks, and decreased cohesive forces. At 298.15 K, the percentage deviations for the Tamura-Kurata (TK) model remain below ~6% across the entire mole fraction range, suggesting reasonably good agreement with experimental values. The Hind and Dey-Biswas (DB) models also predict viscosities satisfactorily, though deviations become larger at higher mole fractions of 2-propenol. At 308.15 K, the DB model shows significant overestimation, with deviations exceeding 19% at equimolar composition, while

$$\ln \eta = X_1 \ln \eta_1 + X_2 \ln \eta_2 + J_0 \left[\frac{X_1 X_2}{T} \right] + J_1 \left[\frac{X_1 X_2 (X_1 - X_2)}{T} \right] + J_2 \left[\frac{X_1 X_2 (X_1 - X_2)^2}{T} \right] \quad (5)$$

TK and Hind models continue to provide better predictions. At 318.15 K, deviations for the DB model rise drastically (up to ~33% near equimolar mixtures), reflecting its inadequacy in capturing the strong specific interactions present in the system at elevated temperatures. In contrast, the TK model exhibits deviations below 3% for most compositions, making it the most reliable predictive tool for this binary system. The absolute percentage deviations ($\% \Delta \eta$) of the theoretical models with respect to experimental

values show a strong dependence on both composition and temperature. At lower temperatures (298.15 K), all three models describe the viscosity behavior relatively well, whereas at higher temperatures (318.15 K), the discrepancies become more pronounced, particularly for the DB model. This trend suggests that specific interactions (hydrogen bonding and dipole–dipole forces) weaken with increasing temperature, and some models fail to adequately account for the complex interplay of these forces. The systematic decrease in viscosity with increasing mole fraction of 2-propenol can be attributed to the disruption of the strong hydrogen-bond network of benzyl alcohol by 2-propenol molecules, leading to structural loosening and free volume enhancement. The better predictive performance of the TK model suggests that non-ideal contributions and interaction parameters considered in this model more closely reflect the real behavior of the binary system. The values of density (ρ_{mix}), experimental viscosity (η_{exp}), and the calculated viscosities from the Tamura–Kurata (η_{TK}), Dey–Biswas (η_{DB}), and Hind (η_{Hind}) models for the binary mixtures of 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol at 298.15, 308.15, and 318.15 K are presented in Table 2. The corresponding absolute percentage deviations ($\% \Delta \eta$) were used to assess the predictive accuracy of the models. At 298.15 K, the viscosity of the mixtures decreases from 10.67 mPa·s at $X_1 = 0.05$ to 2.28 mPa·s at $X_1 = 0.95$, reflecting the dilution of the more viscous 2-phenyl ethanol with the relatively less viscous 2-propenol. The Hind model demonstrates the best predictive capability across the composition range, with deviations between 0.30–7.05%. The Tamura–Kurata relation overestimates viscosity values, particularly at intermediate mole fractions ($X_1 = 0.25$ – 0.55), where deviations rise to 14.47%. The Dey–Biswas model consistently underestimates viscosity, with maximum deviations of 14.29%. This behavior indicates that at lower temperatures, specific hydrogen-bonding and π – π interactions between the hydroxyl group of 2-propenol and the aromatic ring of 2-phenyl ethanol are significant, which are better captured by the Hind approach. At 308.15 K, a marked decrease in viscosity is observed (from 7.05 to 1.69 mPa·s), as higher temperature weakens molecular association. The models show improved agreement with experimental data compared to 298.15 K. Both Tamura–Kurata and Hind relations predict viscosities reasonably well,

with average deviations below 5% across most mole fractions. The Hind model again shows the lowest deviations (0.24–4.55%), whereas the Dey–Biswas model slightly under predicts viscosities, especially in the intermediate composition region. This suggests that moderate heating partially disrupts hydrogen bonding, and theoretical mixing rules perform more satisfactorily. At 318.15 K, the viscosity further decreases from 4.95 mPa·s ($X_1 = 0.05$) to 1.30 mPa·s ($X_1 = 0.95$). At this higher temperature, the predictive ability of the Tamura–Kurata and Dey–Biswas models deteriorates significantly, with deviations reaching 18–19% at $X_1 = 0.50$ – 0.65 . The Hind relation continues to show better consistency, with deviations below 7% across the entire composition range. The poorer performance of Tamura–Kurata and Dey–Biswas relations at higher temperatures may be attributed to their limited capacity to account for the reduction of specific interactions (hydrogen bonding and dipole–dipole forces), which dominate at lower temperatures but diminish with increasing thermal energy. The differences in viscosity behavior and the accuracy of the applied empirical relations can be further interpreted using fundamental molecular theories. Absolute Rate Theory (Eyring's approach) suggests that the flow of a liquid requires molecules to overcome an energy barrier associated with intermolecular attractions. At 298.15 K, the relatively high viscosity and the superior agreement with the Hind relation indicate that the molecules experience stronger associative forces, mainly hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl groups and π – π interactions involving the aromatic ring of 2-phenyl ethanol. As temperature rises, the additional thermal energy lowers this activation barrier, resulting in decreased viscosity and weaker associations. In contrast, Free Volume Theory considers viscosity as dependent on the amount of vacant space within the liquid that allows molecular displacement. With heating, the free volume expands, facilitating molecular mobility and further reducing viscosity. The increasing deviations observed for the Tamura–Kurata and Dey–Biswas models at 318.15 K suggest that these relations are less capable of incorporating such free-volume effects, whereas the Hind equation continues to represent the system more satisfactorily. Overall, the experimental findings reveal that the viscosity of the binary mixture is governed by a delicate balance between specific molecular interactions and thermal

free-volume expansion, and only models that effectively capture both aspects yield reliable predictions. The reliability of the Tamura–Kurata, Dey–Biswas, and Hind relations was further evaluated through average absolute percentage deviation (AAPD) values for both binary mixtures, namely 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol and 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol, at 298.15, 308.15, and 318.15 K (Table 3). For the 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol system, the Hind relation consistently provides the lowest deviations, with AAPD values ranging from 1.88% to 1.00% across the studied temperatures. The Tamura–Kurata relation also shows good predictive ability (1.24–4.17%), though it is slightly less accurate than Hind. In contrast, the Dey–Biswas equation exhibits poor agreement, particularly at elevated temperatures, with deviations rising to 21.88% at 318.15 K. These results indicate that the Hind model effectively incorporates the contributions of associative interactions, while the Dey–Biswas equation fails to capture the effect of temperature on viscosity reduction in this binary system. In the case of the 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol mixture, the predictive performance of the models is more composition and temperature-dependent. At 298.15 K, the Tamura–Kurata relation shows the lowest deviation (2.24%), followed by Hind (3.83%), while the Dey–Biswas equation deviates significantly (9.42%). At 308.15 K, the Hind model again provides the best agreement (2.50%), whereas both Tamura–Kurata (3.05%) and Dey–Biswas (3.32%) display comparable predictive capacity. However, at 318.15 K, Tamura–Kurata exhibits the minimum deviation (1.16%), while Hind shows slightly higher deviation (4.12%), and Dey–Biswas performs poorly with a large deviation of 12.99%. Overall, the Hind relation emerges as the most reliable model for both binary systems, particularly for mixtures involving benzyl alcohol, where associative interactions are dominant. For 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol, the Tamura–Kurata equation also shows competitive performance, especially at higher temperatures where free volume effects dominate over hydrogen bonding. The Dey–Biswas model consistently underperforms, indicating its limited applicability for associating binary mixtures. The Jouyban–Acree (J–A) model was applied to evaluate the viscosity data of the studied binary systems, and the corresponding coefficients (J_0 , J_1 , J_2) along with standard deviations (S.D.) are

listed in Table 4. For the 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol system, the coefficients display strong negative values of J_0 and J_1 at lower temperatures (298.15 K and 308.15 K), reflecting the dominance of hydrogen-bonded associative interactions between the hydroxyl groups of the two alcohols. At 318.15 K, J_0 changes sign and becomes positive (27.704), suggesting a reduced contribution of specific interactions due to thermal disruption, while J_1 and J_2 remain negative, indicating persistent but weakened molecular associations. The standard deviations are very small (0.006–0.071), confirming that the J–A model adequately represents the viscosity behavior. In the case of 2-propenol + 2-phenyl ethanol, the coefficients exhibit different trends. At 298.15 K, J_0 is

highly positive (125.814), accompanied by a moderately negative J_2 , suggesting the significant role of aromatic–alcohol interactions, such as π – π stacking between phenyl groups and hydrogen bonding with propanol. As temperature increases, J_0 decreases (89.296 at 308.15 K) and then increases again (112.895 at 318.15 K), reflecting a dynamic balance between disruption of hydrogen bonds and stabilization of π – π interactions. Interestingly, J_1 shifts from positive at 298.15 K (6.372) to negative values at higher temperatures, implying a change in the nature of composition-dependent interactions. The S.D. values remain low (0.010–0.025), suggesting that the J–A model provides a reliable correlation for this system as well.

Fig1. Plot of η_E of 2-propenol+Benzyl alcohol

Fig2. Plot of η_E of 2-propenol+2-Phenyl ethanol

Figure 1 shows the variation of excess viscosity (η^E) with mole fraction for 2-propanol + benzyl alcohol at three temperatures. At 298.15 K, (η^E) values are negative over the entire composition range, reaching a minimum near equimolar proportion, which reflects structure-breaking effects due to disruption of self-associated hydrogen-bonded structures. At 308.15 K, the magnitude of (η^E) decreases, indicating a reduction in intermolecular association with increasing temperature. By 318.15 K, (η^E) values approach zero, suggesting that dispersion forces dominate over hydrogen bonding at higher temperatures. Model comparisons reveal that the Tamura–Kurata correlation closely follows the experimental trend, while the Hind–Ubbelohde model moderately matches but underestimates deviations at mid-compositions. The Dey–Biswas relation significantly deviates at higher temperatures, even predicting positive values where experimental results remain negative. This confirms that the TK model provides the most reliable description for this binary system across the studied temperatures whereas the excess viscosity (η^E) of 2-propanol + 2-phenylethanol mixture as shown in figure 2 is negative across all compositions and temperatures, with the largest

deviation at 298.15 K around equimolar composition. This indicates predominant structure-breaking interactions due to disruption of hydrogen-bonded networks. With increasing temperature, the magnitude of η^E decreases, reflecting weaker specific interactions and a greater contribution from dispersion forces. Among the models, the Tamura–Kurata relation provides the best agreement with experimental data at all temperatures, particularly capturing the composition dependence.

$$S.D(\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{(\sum_{i=1}^n \eta_{Exp} - \eta_{Theo})^2}{n - p}} \quad (6)$$

The Hind–Ubbelohde model shows moderate agreement, while the Dey–Biswas relation tends to over predict deviations, even yielding spurious positive values at higher temperatures. Overall, the results confirm that temperature reduces non-ideal contributions, and that the TK model is most suitable for describing viscosity behavior in this binary system.

Table1- Density (ρ_{mix}), experimental viscosity (η_{exp}), theoretical viscosities and absolute percentage deviations for 2-propanol + benzyl alcohol mixtures at different temperatures

X_1	ρ_{mix}	η_{exp}	ϕ_1	ϕ_2	η_{TK}	η_{DB}	η_{Hind}	ABS		
								$\% \Delta \eta_{TK}$	$\% \Delta \eta_{DB}$	$\% \Delta \eta_{Hind}$
2-Propenol+Benzyl alcohol										
T=298.15K										
0.05	1.033	5.30	0.04	0.96	5.33	5.31	5.31	0.66	0.20	0.14
0.1	1.024	5.05	0.08	0.92	5.12	5.07	5.07	1.26	0.38	0.25
0.15	1.014	4.80	0.12	0.88	4.90	4.84	4.83	2.18	0.92	0.70
0.2	1.004	4.56	0.16	0.84	4.69	4.62	4.61	2.97	1.38	1.07
0.25	0.994	4.33	0.20	0.80	4.49	4.41	4.39	3.64	1.77	1.35
0.3	0.984	4.12	0.24	0.76	4.29	4.20	4.18	4.21	2.12	1.59
0.35	0.973	3.91	0.29	0.71	4.09	4.01	3.98	4.66	2.41	1.77
0.4	0.961	3.71	0.33	0.67	3.90	3.82	3.79	5.07	2.72	1.96
0.45	0.949	3.52	0.38	0.62	3.72	3.63	3.60	5.50	3.11	2.22
0.5	0.937	3.34	0.43	0.57	3.54	3.46	3.42	6.03	3.66	2.66
0.55	0.924	3.17	0.48	0.52	3.36	3.29	3.25	6.06	3.79	2.68
0.6	0.911	3.01	0.53	0.47	3.19	3.13	3.09	6.04	3.92	2.73
0.65	0.897	2.86	0.58	0.42	3.03	2.97	2.94	5.97	4.06	2.81
0.7	0.882	2.72	0.63	0.37	2.87	2.83	2.79	5.77	4.12	2.84
0.75	0.867	2.58	0.69	0.31	2.72	2.69	2.65	5.48	4.13	2.87
0.8	0.852	2.46	0.75	0.25	2.58	2.55	2.52	4.80	3.78	2.60
0.85	0.835	2.35	0.81	0.19	2.44	2.43	2.40	4.10	3.40	2.37
0.9	0.818	2.25	0.87	0.13	2.31	2.30	2.29	2.79	2.39	1.61

0.95	0.800	2.15	0.93	0.07	2.19	2.19	2.18	2.13	1.97	1.52
					T=308.15K					
0.05	1.025	3.91	0.04	0.96	3.93	4.00	3.91	0.55	2.28	0.04
0.1	1.016	3.73	0.08	0.92	3.77	3.90	3.74	1.14	4.58	0.15
0.15	1.006	3.56	0.12	0.88	3.62	3.80	3.57	1.65	6.74	0.21
0.2	0.997	3.39	0.16	0.84	3.46	3.69	3.40	2.20	8.90	0.36
0.25	0.986	3.23	0.20	0.80	3.31	3.58	3.24	2.60	10.81	0.38
0.3	0.976	3.08	0.24	0.76	3.17	3.46	3.09	2.97	12.59	0.44
0.35	0.965	2.92	0.29	0.71	3.02	3.34	2.94	3.53	14.46	0.73
0.4	0.953	2.77	0.33	0.67	2.88	3.22	2.80	4.06	16.14	1.04
0.45	0.941	2.63	0.38	0.62	2.75	3.09	2.67	4.46	17.51	1.29
0.5	0.929	2.49	0.43	0.57	2.62	2.96	2.54	5.07	18.90	1.81
0.55	0.916	2.37	0.48	0.52	2.49	2.83	2.41	4.99	19.25	1.72
0.6	0.902	2.26	0.53	0.47	2.36	2.69	2.29	4.80	19.20	1.60
0.65	0.889	2.15	0.58	0.42	2.24	2.55	2.18	4.65	18.86	1.60
0.7	0.874	2.04	0.63	0.37	2.13	2.41	2.07	4.30	17.93	1.48
0.75	0.859	1.95	0.69	0.31	2.02	2.27	1.97	3.78	16.40	1.28
0.8	0.843	1.85	0.75	0.25	1.91	2.12	1.88	3.43	14.60	1.31
0.85	0.827	1.76	0.81	0.19	1.81	1.98	1.79	3.05	12.28	1.38
0.9	0.809	1.68	0.87	0.13	1.72	1.83	1.70	2.72	9.46	1.56
0.95	0.791	1.60	0.93	0.07	1.63	1.69	1.62	1.89	5.54	1.29
					T=318.15K					
0.05	1.017	2.99	0.04	0.96	3.00	3.11	2.98	0.25	4.01	0.25
0.1	1.008	2.86	0.08	0.92	2.88	3.09	2.85	0.40	7.87	0.58
0.15	0.998	2.75	0.12	0.88	2.76	3.06	2.72	0.41	11.49	0.99
0.2	0.988	2.63	0.16	0.84	2.64	3.02	2.59	0.44	14.99	1.36
0.25	0.978	2.51	0.20	0.80	2.53	2.97	2.47	0.49	18.33	1.66
0.3	0.967	2.40	0.24	0.76	2.41	2.91	2.35	0.56	21.46	1.89
0.35	0.956	2.29	0.29	0.71	2.30	2.85	2.24	0.84	24.54	1.86
0.4	0.945	2.17	0.33	0.67	2.20	2.77	2.13	1.18	27.35	1.72
0.45	0.933	2.06	0.38	0.62	2.09	2.68	2.03	1.70	29.95	1.36
0.5	0.920	1.95	0.43	0.57	1.99	2.57	1.93	2.06	31.84	1.08
0.55	0.907	1.86	0.48	0.52	1.90	2.46	1.84	2.02	32.63	1.12
0.6	0.894	1.77	0.53	0.47	1.80	2.34	1.75	1.82	32.52	1.25
0.65	0.880	1.68	0.58	0.42	1.71	2.22	1.66	1.79	31.88	1.14
0.7	0.865	1.59	0.64	0.36	1.62	2.08	1.58	1.79	30.44	0.93
0.75	0.850	1.51	0.69	0.31	1.54	1.94	1.50	1.82	28.16	0.61
0.8	0.834	1.43	0.75	0.25	1.46	1.79	1.43	1.71	24.73	0.35
0.85	0.818	1.36	0.81	0.19	1.38	1.64	1.36	1.73	20.49	0.10
0.9	0.801	1.30	0.87	0.13	1.31	1.48	1.30	1.22	14.63	0.09
0.95	0.782	1.23	0.93	0.07	1.24	1.33	1.24	1.27	8.44	0.69

Table2- Density (ρ_{mix}), experimental viscosity (η_{exp}), theoretical viscosities and absolute percentage deviations for 2-propenol + 2- phenyl ethanol mixtures at different temperatures

X_1	ρ_{mix}	η_{exp}	ϕ_1	ϕ_2	η_{TK}	η_{DB}	η_{Hind}	ABS		
								$\% \Delta \eta_{TK}$	$\% \Delta \eta_{DB}$	$\% \Delta \eta_{Hind}$
2-Propenol+2-Phenyl ethanol										

					T=298.15K					
0.05	1.009	10.67	0.03	0.97	10.76	10.47	10.63	0.87	1.81	0.30
0.1	1.002	9.93	0.07	0.93	10.12	9.60	9.89	1.91	3.31	0.41
0.15	0.994	9.26	0.10	0.90	9.50	8.80	9.18	2.65	4.93	0.77
0.2	0.986	8.62	0.14	0.86	8.89	8.06	8.51	3.21	6.52	1.26
0.25	0.978	8.00	0.18	0.82	8.30	7.37	7.87	3.78	7.89	1.68
0.3	0.969	7.41	0.22	0.78	7.73	6.74	7.25	4.31	9.07	2.06
0.35	0.960	6.86	0.26	0.74	7.17	6.15	6.68	4.50	10.28	2.66
0.4	0.950	6.35	0.30	0.70	6.63	5.62	6.13	4.33	11.52	3.48
0.45	0.940	5.86	0.34	0.66	6.10	5.13	5.61	4.11	12.49	4.22
0.5	0.929	5.41	0.39	0.61	5.60	4.68	5.13	3.49	13.46	5.17
0.55	0.918	4.98	0.44	0.56	5.12	4.28	4.68	2.87	14.07	5.94
0.6	0.906	4.57	0.49	0.51	4.66	3.91	4.26	2.04	14.47	6.71
0.65	0.894	4.17	0.54	0.46	4.23	3.58	3.88	1.42	14.29	7.05
0.7	0.880	3.79	0.60	0.40	3.83	3.28	3.53	0.89	13.60	7.05
0.75	0.866	3.44	0.66	0.34	3.45	3.01	3.20	0.36	12.48	6.80
0.8	0.851	3.10	0.72	0.28	3.10	2.77	2.92	0.11	10.66	5.98
0.85	0.835	2.81	0.78	0.22	2.79	2.56	2.66	0.57	8.85	5.31
0.9	0.819	2.54	0.85	0.15	2.52	2.38	2.43	1.01	6.53	4.20
0.95	0.801	2.28	0.92	0.08	2.28	2.22	2.24	0.15	2.84	1.71
					T=308.15K					
0.05	1.009	7.05	0.03	0.97	7.11	7.09	7.03	0.86	0.51	0.24
0.1	1.002	6.59	0.07	0.93	6.71	6.67	6.57	1.76	1.11	0.40
0.15	0.994	6.15	0.10	0.90	6.32	6.26	6.12	2.77	1.87	0.42
0.2	0.986	5.73	0.14	0.86	5.94	5.87	5.70	3.65	2.56	0.52
0.25	0.978	5.34	0.18	0.82	5.56	5.50	5.29	4.12	2.91	0.96
0.3	0.969	4.97	0.22	0.78	5.20	5.13	4.90	4.57	3.33	1.33
0.35	0.960	4.62	0.26	0.74	4.84	4.79	4.54	4.78	3.59	1.85
0.4	0.950	4.29	0.30	0.70	4.50	4.45	4.19	4.95	3.90	2.28
0.45	0.940	3.96	0.34	0.66	4.17	4.13	3.86	5.10	4.30	2.62
0.5	0.929	3.67	0.39	0.61	3.85	3.83	3.55	4.80	4.35	3.21
0.55	0.918	3.39	0.44	0.56	3.54	3.54	3.26	4.44	4.43	3.70
0.6	0.906	3.12	0.49	0.51	3.25	3.26	2.99	3.93	4.45	4.14
0.65	0.894	2.88	0.54	0.46	2.97	3.00	2.75	3.24	4.35	4.55
0.7	0.880	2.63	0.60	0.40	2.71	2.75	2.52	2.79	4.53	4.50
0.75	0.866	2.41	0.66	0.34	2.46	2.52	2.31	2.33	4.66	4.22
0.8	0.851	2.20	0.72	0.28	2.24	2.30	2.12	1.65	4.45	3.90
0.85	0.835	2.01	0.78	0.22	2.03	2.09	1.94	1.11	4.13	3.22
0.9	0.819	1.86	0.85	0.15	1.85	1.90	1.79	0.65	2.12	3.53
0.95	0.801	1.69	0.92	0.08	1.69	1.72	1.66	0.42	1.47	1.84
					T=318.15K					
0.05	0.994	4.95	0.03	0.97	4.96	5.05	4.91	0.12	1.87	0.91
0.1	0.987	4.65	0.07	0.93	4.69	4.85	4.60	0.98	4.51	1.04
0.15	0.979	4.37	0.10	0.90	4.43	4.66	4.30	1.41	6.73	1.56
0.2	0.971	4.10	0.14	0.86	4.17	4.46	4.01	1.64	8.73	2.21
0.25	0.962	3.85	0.18	0.82	3.92	4.26	3.74	1.79	10.62	2.87

0.3	0.953	3.60	0.22	0.78	3.67	4.05	3.48	2.04	12.59	3.35
0.35	0.944	3.36	0.26	0.74	3.43	3.84	3.23	2.17	14.36	3.87
0.4	0.934	3.13	0.30	0.70	3.20	3.63	3.00	2.27	16.03	4.30
0.45	0.924	2.91	0.35	0.65	2.98	3.42	2.78	2.30	17.49	4.68
0.5	0.913	2.71	0.39	0.61	2.76	3.21	2.57	1.83	18.22	5.39
0.55	0.902	2.52	0.44	0.56	2.55	2.99	2.37	1.22	18.56	6.08
0.6	0.890	2.34	0.49	0.51	2.36	2.78	2.19	0.60	18.61	6.61
0.65	0.877	2.16	0.54	0.46	2.17	2.56	2.02	0.23	18.60	6.72
0.7	0.864	1.99	0.60	0.40	1.99	2.35	1.86	0.04	18.26	6.54
0.75	0.849	1.82	0.66	0.34	1.82	2.14	1.71	0.13	17.56	5.98
0.8	0.834	1.67	0.72	0.28	1.66	1.94	1.58	0.01	16.40	5.00
0.85	0.818	1.53	0.79	0.21	1.52	1.74	1.46	0.26	13.90	4.17
0.9	0.801	1.42	0.85	0.15	1.39	1.54	1.36	1.56	9.15	4.18
0.95	0.783	1.30	0.92	0.08	1.28	1.36	1.26	1.47	4.65	2.77

Table3-Average absolute % deviations of Tamura-kurata, Dey-Biswas and Hind model at different Temperature

2-Propenol+Benzyl alcohol				2-propanol+2-phenylethanol		
T/K	AAPD			AAPD		
	η_{TK}	η_{DB}	η_{Hind}	η_{TK}	η_{DB}	η_{Hind}
298.15	4.17	2.643	1.881	2.241	9.424	3.83
308.150	3.25	12.971	1.035	3.048	3.318	2.50
318.150	1.24	21.882	1.002	1.162	12.991	4.12

Table4- Numerical coefficient and Standard deviation calculated by Joubyan Acree model from 298.15-318.15K

2-Propenol+Benzyl alcohol					2-Propanol+2-Phenylethanol			
T/K	J_0	J_1	J_2	S.D	J_0	J_1	J_2	S.D
298.15	-21.193	-45.511	-20.006	0.006	125.814	6.372	-42.131	0.025
308.15	-8.592	-40.288	-13.115	0.006	89.296	-11.115	-26.406	0.010
318.15	27.704	-39.225	-20.007	0.071	112.895	-2.764	-18.964	0.010

CONCLUSION

The present investigation provides comprehensive insight into the viscous and thermo physical behavior of two binary liquid mixtures 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol and 2-propenol + 2-phenylethanol over the temperature range 298.15–318.15 K. The systematic decrease in viscosity and density with increasing mole fraction of 2-propenol and temperature confirms the breakdown of intermolecular hydrogen bonding and enhanced free volume in both systems. Comparative analysis of semi-empirical models reveals that the **Hind relation** exhibits the best predictive accuracy for both mixtures, particularly for 2-propenol + benzyl alcohol, where associative interactions dominate. The **Tamura–Kurata equation** also

performs satisfactorily, especially for the 2-propenol + 2-phenylethanol system at higher temperatures, where dispersion forces and free-volume effects become significant. In contrast, the **Dey–Biswas model** consistently shows larger deviations, indicating its limited applicability to associating systems. The **Jouyban–Acree model** successfully correlates viscosity data across all temperatures, yielding very low standard deviations and capturing the temperature-dependent variation of molecular interactions. The negative excess viscosity values throughout the composition range suggest predominant structure-breaking interactions in both systems. The results demonstrate that the non-ideal behavior of these binary mixtures arises from a complex interplay of hydrogen bonding, dipole–

dipole, and dispersion forces. The validated models, particularly Hind and Tamura–Kurata, offer reliable tools for predicting viscosity behavior of alcohol-based mixtures relevant to chemical, pharmaceutical, and process industries.

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